

silicates were filtered off and filtrate was concentrated. These extracts were used for tlc. The R_f values of individual cations were calculated by the usual procedure.

Results and Discussion

Various experiments were carried out at room temperature to study the effect of pH, concentration of glycolic acid and development time for chromatoplates (Table 1) on the R_f values of individual cations. R_f value measurements were done in triplicate for each set of determination.

TABLE 1 - VARIATION OF R_f VALUES WITH DEVELOPMENT TIME

Time min	Glycolic acid = 0.05 M, pH = 2.5 Metal ions with R_f					
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	Pb	Mn
5	0.40	0.60	0.44	0.41	0.41	0.59
10	0.31	0.66	0.42	0.44	0.40	0.66
15	0.33	0.73	0.46	0.48	0.46	0.63

Both thin layer adsorption and partition chromatography techniques were tried. However, in the present investigation, partition chromatography has been preferred over adsorption technique as the former requires less time for the development of chromatoplates. The variation in R_f values with pH at 0.1 M glycolic acid reveals that at pH 1 most of the cations move with the solvent front, while at pH 2.5 there is a considerable difference in the R_f values of various cations leading to good separation of metal ions. Therefore, pH 2.5 was fixed for all measurements.

It is observed that R_f values changes with the change in concentration of mobile phase. There is increase in R_f values of most of the cations with increase in concentration of glycolic acid solution. However, it has been found that there is significant difference in R_f values of cations at 0.05M concentration of mobile phase and good separations are possible at this concentration. Therefore, higher concentrations of glycolic acid were avoided and 0.05M concentration was fixed for further studies. The perusal of Table 1 reveals the effect of time on the R_f values of individual cations and it reveals that binary and ternary separations are possible in 5 and 10 min respectively. The method has been applied for the separations of ternary $Fe^{III}/Ni^{II}/M(II)$ and $Fe^{III}/Mn^{II}/M(II)$ (where M = Cu, Zn and Pb) in 10 min time.

The present method has also been employed for separation and detection of metal ions from the mineral samples from different mines of Udaipur district (Rajasthan). The results (Table 2) show excellent reproducibility, and the variation does not exceed 2% of average R_f values.

TABLE 2 - SEPARATION OF METAL IONS FROM MINERAL SAMPLES

Glycolic acid = 0.05 M, pH = 2.5, Time of development = 15 min

Samples no *	Metal ion %			R_f values		
	Fe	Pb	Mn	Fe	Pb	Mn
1	7.56	0.83	0.22	0.31	0.40	0.67
2	7.24	0.85	0.18	0.31	0.40	0.67
3	7.30	7.30	0.25	0.31	0.43	0.66

*From Baleria mines.

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Gold(III)-Gelatin Complex. A Specific Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Hydrazine and Formaldehyde in Water

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THE search for simple methods of determinations of both hydrazine and formaldehyde are of importance in analytical chemistry¹⁻³. There are a good number of methods^{2,4} for determining hydrazine and formaldehyde. In this communication a simple, non-toxic alkaline active reagent (reduction of Au^{III} -gelatin complex) for the direct spectrophotometric (at 540 nm) determinations of formaldehyde and hydrazine is proposed.

Experimental

All absorbance measurements were made on a Shimadzu UV-160 digital spectrophotometer with 1-cm quartz cells. A ECIL digital pH-meter was used for pH measurements.

A stock solution of gold(III) chloride ($10^{-3}M$) was prepared by dissolving chloroauric acid (Johnson Matthey) in double-distilled water and standardised⁵. Fresh stock solution (0.1M) of formaldehyde (Aldrich) was prepared and standardised⁶. A fresh stock solution of hydrazine (0.1M) was prepared by dissolving hydrazine sulphate in distilled water and standardised⁷. Gelatin (E. Merck) solution (1%) was prepared in warm distilled water. Glycine buffer of pH 9.5 was prepared by mixing 0.2 M glycine (50 ml) and 0.2 M sodium hydroxide (16.8 ml) to obtain 200 ml and the pH was adjusted.

Results and Discussion

Aliquots (5 ml) of $4.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ gold(III) chloride solution was placed in a series of 50-ml volumetric flasks. Then 1% gelatin solution (20 ml) was added for complexation of gold(III) ion at about 30°. pH of the solution was adjusted to about 9.5 using glycine buffer. Finally, to the solution of gold(III)-gelatin complex, a solution (0.2–5.0 ml) of hydrazine or formaldehyde ($10^{-1} M$) were introduced. After 3 h the absorbance values was noted at 540 nm and at room temperature (30°) against water after diluting the solution to 50 ml.

The absorption spectra of the gold sol solution show a maximum absorbance at 540 nm without any scattering. However, the unreduced gold(III)-gelatin complex does not absorb at all at 540 nm which simply enables the determination without any reagent blank. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

No. of observations	Amount of solution (ml), containing $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ of		λ_{max} (at 540 nm)
	Hydrazine	Formaldehyde	
1.	0.10	—	0.26
2.	0.20	—	0.44
3.	0.25	—	0.54
4.	0.50	—	1.06
5.	0.80	—	1.48
6.	—	0.5	0.11
7.	—	1.5	0.30
8.	—	2.4	0.51
9.	—	3.0	0.64
10.	—	4.0	0.86

The reduction of gold(III)-gelatin complex at room temperature (30°) is influenced by pH and

goes quickly to completion at pH 8.0–11.0. The acidic or neutral pH condition is not suitable for gold(III)-gelatin binding.

The complexation of gold(III) ion and *in situ* stabilisation of the pink sol require about 20.0 ml of 1% gelatin solution. Increase in the amount of gelatin did not hinder the determination. The reduction of gold(III)-gelatin complex at 30–50° takes only 1 h for quantitative reduction of the complex. At temperature below 25°, the reduction rate was very slow, and above 50°, fast reduction produced aggregated gold sol causing irreproducible absorbance values.

The entities which do not interfere in any one of the determinations when present in amounts upto 20–25 M excess of hydrazine or formaldehyde include glucose, sucrose, tartaric acid, amino acids, alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and their chlorides, nitrates, sulphates and acetates. Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} do not interfere if they are masked by Na_4 -EDTA solution. However, in the determination of formaldehyde, aldehydes only interfere strongly but the wavelengths of maximum absorbances and molar absorptivities differ.

The advantage of the proposed method over other classical methods is that the reaction goes to completion quickly in alkaline medium which may rule out the problems of its determination under acidic condition.

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